

THERMAL PROPERTIES AND STABILITY OF PET-HEMP FIBERS COMPOSITES

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1 General Introduction

During the past decades, composites materials made of thermoplastic matrices reinforced with natural fibers have been highly applied in numerous engineering fields. These materials have also been highly investigated as shown by the wide range of publications dealing with it [1–5]. Furthermore, they represent such a diverse and important group of materials with many more unexplored aspects. This paper investigates the thermal properties and thermal stability of polyethylene terephthalate (PET), a high melting thermoplastic ($T_m > 200^\circ\text{C}$), reinforced with hemp fibers. The thermal properties and stability are crucial composite materials parameters, as they are known to have a huge impact on both their forming process and their performance [6–10].

The growing interest in natural fibers reinforced composites is justified by the numerous advantages they offer. These include their low weight, low cost, non-corrosiveness, recyclability, renewability, and low energy processing [11–13]. Further expansion of these applications is however hindered by numerous challenges, such as the thermal degradation of natural fibers, especially during processing at high temperature. Most of the actual applications are therefore restricted to lower melting thermoplastics [4]. In this regard, although composite materials of high melting thermoplastics reinforced with natural fibers represent an appreciable potential for engineering applications, they are still under-exploited. The main sources for such limitations of their use have not been previously investigated; however they can either be related to their processing challenges, or to variations of their thermal properties. An example of their processing challenges is represented by the melting point of their matrices which by definition is higher than the onset of thermal degradation of natural fibers. Finally, engineering designs with such composite

materials would be highly impacted by the high melting range, as it affects both fibers' thermal degradation, and composites' properties variations. Furthermore, such variations would be important for composites parameters such as crystallinity, and multistage processing.

In the contrary of low melting thermoplastics, very few works have been reported on high melting thermoplastics reinforced with natural fibers, respectively by Caulfield et al., Field et al., Tan et al., and Bo Madsen. Caulfield et al. have extruded PA 6 and PA 6,6 with high purity wood pulp fiber [14]; Field et al. have used a solvent mixture for the compounding of PET and cellulose [15]; Tan et al. have processed Unsaturated Polyester Resin (UPR) from recycled PET, which was subsequently reinforced with alkaline treated empty fruit bunch (EFB)[16]; and Bo Madsen have processed PET reinforced with hemp fibers through the winding of both filaments followed by thermo compression [17]. In some previous works, the effects of various additives and fiber loads in the mechanical properties of PET-hemp composites were studied; in addition to their application in the design of a PET-hemp fibers composite I-Beam [18–20]. The thermal properties and stabilities of polyolefins and low temperature processing thermosets reinforced with natural fibers, have been reported in the most part by authors like Bacaloglu et al, Shih, Varghese et al., and Peterson et al [8], [10], [21], [22].

It is quite advantageous to reinforce PET with hemp fibers. These advantages include the environmental impacts of polymer recycling during processing, the resulting composite's toughness provided by the aromatic rings of PET, and the reduction of the rate of stress concentration in the composite parts during melt processing, as a result of the similarities between its constituents' densities. Finally, due to the high glass transition temperature ($T_g = 60^\circ\text{C}$) of PET, the processed composite parts are solid at room

temperature. This work is a case study of the effects of fibers and processing conditions on the thermal properties of high melting thermoplastics reinforced with of natural fibers; and it is of utmost importance for multistage processing applications such as thermoforming.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

PET, grade AA-48 (Eastman, QC, Canada), PCL (Sigma Aldrich, Oakville, ON, Canada), and hemp fibers of composite grade (Lanaupôle, Berthierville, QC, Canada) were used in this work. These fibers had an average length and diameter of 6 cm and 20-25 μ m respectively.

2.2 Methodology

PET and hemp fibers were modified through selected applications to allow melt processing with limited thermal degradation, and to create an improved interface. The thermal stability of the resulting composite formulations and their thermal properties were respectively tested with a TGA (Q50), and a DSC (Q20), both from TA Instrument, (New Castle, DE, USA).

PET-hemp composites with 1%, 5%, 10%, 15%, and 20% (w/w) fibers were investigated. Processing was done in two stages to include compounding in a torque batch mixer (Haake Rheomix, polylab OS system, USA) at the mixing chamber's temperature of 240°C, 250°C, and 260°C; followed by injection molding at 250°C with a Haake-Minijet. The mold was kept at 50°C during injection molding. PET and the various composite formulations were pre-dried at 150°C for 4 hours prior to processing. Such pre-drying process was essential to avoid sample degradation due to the hygroscopic nature of both PET and hemp fibers [1].

The DSC experiments involved a series of steps including sample equilibration at 0°C, a 10 minutes isotherm, a sample temperature ramp up at 20°C/min to a maximum temperature of 300°C, followed

by another 10 minutes isotherm, and finally a temperature ramp down at 10°C/min. After the first run, the data for various formulation groups were monitored and compared with those of the samples compounded at 250°C, and cooled without isotherm after the maximum temperature was reached. Such study was the basis for the analysis of the effects of moisture absorption and thermal degradation on multistage processing. Nitrogen was used as an inert gas in all DSC experiments both to avoid thermo oxidation of the sample and for cooling purposes.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Thermal stability

The thermal stability of both the composites and their constituents are given by Fig. 1, Fig. 2, Fig. 3, and Fig. 4. Data analysis was done with an in-built TA's universal analysis software.

Fig. 1 shows the thermal stability of the various composite constituents. It shows that both matrices are stable below 400°C. In addition, the alkaline treated hemp fibers show an appreciable stability below 300°C.

Furthermore,

Fig. 2, Fig. 3, and Fig. 4 show the thermal stability of PET-hemp fibers composites compounded respectively with a mixing chamber at 240°C, 250°C, and 260°C. In each case, all the formulations appear to have a good stability below 300°C; however, there is less impact by the mixing chamber's temperature. However, an increase of the fiber load results in an increase of the composite's rate of thermal degradations.

Such constituents' thermal stability which have initially being studied by many authors such as those referenced in [8], [23], [24] are advantageous parameters especially for processing high melting thermoplastics with natural fibers and their engineering applications.

3.2 Thermal properties

The heat capacities of the various studied composite formulations are given by Fig. 5, Fig. 6, Fig. 7, Fig. 8, Fig. 9, and Fig. 10. They are better analyzed in two groups according to the experimental cycle.

The first group made of Fig. 5, Fig. 6, and Fig. 7 relates to the first DSC experimental run, while the second made of Fig. 8, Fig. 9, and Fig. 10 relates to the second run.

The data was obtained by the heat capacity analysis using TA's in-built analysis which was validated by the literature data for PET [25]. In all the analytical stages, sapphire's data were used for references.

Three important areas exist in the sample of the first experimental run. They appear respectively like peaks with onsets at 60°C, 125°C, and 240°C respectively. Following the comparison with literature values such as [26], [27], these peaks either correspond or are directly related to the glass transition temperature of PET, the crystallization, and the melting temperature of PET. The high intensity of the first peak also suggests the existence of free PCL chains and the contribution of their melting point to the first peak.

At room temperature, the heat capacities of all the composite formulations follow the inequality $0.5 < C_p < 1.5$ [J/g/°C] for the data of the first experimental run, and the maximum values around 5[J/g/°C] at the melting peak of PET.

The PET's melt peak intensity appeared to vary with the mixing chamber's temperature and the fiber's load. Although there are a few observed exceptions, the heat capacity of the samples tends to lower with an increase of the fibers load, especially at PET's melting peak. The highest intensity was found for the composites compounded with a mixing chamber at 240°C; however the data for the samples compounded with a mixing chamber at 250°C and 260°C were comparable.

Still on the graphs related to the first experimental DSC run, no difference is shown on the onsets of both the melting and crystallization, however the

associated heat vary with the fiber's load. No specific trend can however be found. The heat capacity shows significant variations.

A second group made of Fig. 8, Fig. 9, and Fig. 10 describes some thermal properties related to the second experimental run. They show two major differences with respect to the observations of Fig. 5, Fig. 6, and Fig. 7.

The first noticeable difference is the disappearance of the first peaks. Such event is likely linked to samples' annealing and crystallization. We suggest that the 10 minutes isothermal stage at 300°C may have cause some thermal degradation of hemp fibers leading to even further crystallization. Such observation had been previously made by other authors like Nabar [26]. Another suggestion for such crystalline structure is the concentration of the samples' heat capacity around 1 [J/g/°C] for the data of the second experimental run, contrary to more dispersed values in the first run. The disappearance of the first peaks indicates the non existence of free PCL chains and a good structural network. More work still has to done for characterizing the networking of the various composite constituents in the studied formulations.

The second difference if the maximum values of the heat capacity which appears to have been lowered below 5 J/g/°C.

For both the first and the second experimental runs, the heat capacities of the composite samples compounded at 250°C showed significantly different results from those compounded at 240°C and 260°C.

In addition, although the DSC curves are not shown here, they showed minimal memory effects, especially during their second cycles. Since all the formulations have undergone the same pre-testing treatment, the difference between the formulations compounded at 250°C and those compounded at 260°C and 240°C could be attributed to the impact of the extent of polymer melting on fiber-matrix interactions. In fact such interaction have been found by other authors to affects the chain mobility and cristallinity of the composite samples [28–30].

3.3 Effects of the fibers' thermal degradation between DSC runs 1 and 2

Fig. 11 shows a compilation of the samples' weight loss following the 10 minutes isotherm at maximum temperature of the first experimental run. It also includes a set of formulation compounded with the mixing chamber at 250°C, and tested without isotherm at the maximum temperature.

The observed weight loss appears to be related to both the fiber load and the temperature of the mixing chamber. Just as for the case of the heat capacities, the weight loss by the samples compounded with the mixing chamber at 260°C and 250°C are comparable, while it increases with the fiber load for the sample compounded with the mixing chamber at 250°C. The appreciable trend for the last group of samples can also be related to the extent of polymer melting and its chain mobility. The formulations compounded with the mixing chamber at 250°C and tested without isotherm at 300°C showed no weight loss. In all the cases however, the observed significant weight loss can either be attributed to moisture absorption by the samples or by the thermal degradation of the fibers during the isothermal step.

No significant sample weight loss was observed following sample drying prior to the first experimental DSC run. This observation is in agreement with the thermal stability of the composite formulations previously discussed and described by Fig. 2, Fig. 3, and Fig. 4. The weight loss can then be related in the most part to fiber degradation during the isothermal step at 300°C. This is confirmed by the observation of no weight loss in the absence of the isothermal step at 300°C. Such thermal degradation of the fibers increases the crystallization process of the samples, and is in agreement with previous observations made by other authors like Nabar [26].

4 Conclusion

PET-hemp composites were processed with various hemp loads, through compounding at different

mixing chamber's temperatures. The stability of the formulation was studied alongside some of their heat capacity.

All the formulations were found to be thermally stable within the time limit of classical plastic-composites' processing. Some differences were noted between two DSC cycles, especially when the samples were isothermally heated once the maximum temperature was reached.

Our results suggest the existence of some hemp fiber's degradation as a function of the fiber load and processing time. Such results are important parameters for multistage processing. However, such thermal degradation may have a good impact on the samples' crystallinity, thus the importance of fine tuning the processing parameters with respect to the needed applications.

These results are another indication of the potential of reinforcing high melting thermoplastics like PET with natural fibers for engineering applications. Additional work is still being done on relating the presented observations to the structural parameters of the studied composites; in view of a future journal publication.

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Fig. 1: Thermal degradation of various composite constituents (PCL, PET, virgin and alkaline treated hemp fibers)

Fig. 3: Thermal degradation of PET-hemp fiber composites, compounded in at 250°C mixing chamber

Fig. 2: Thermal stability of PET-hemp fiber composites, compounded in 240°C mixing chamber

Fig. 4: Thermal degradation of PET-hemp fiber composites, compounded at 260°C mixing chamber

Fig. 5: Heat capacities of PET-hemp composites compounded in a 240°C mixing chamber, data from the first experimental run

Fig. 7: Heat capacities of PET-hemp composites compounded in a 260°C mixing chamber, data from the first experimental run

Fig. 6: Heat capacities of PET-hemp composites compounded in a 250°C mixing chamber, data from the first experimental run

Fig. 8: Heat capacities of PET-hemp composites compounded in a 240°C mixing chamber, data from the second experimental run

Fig. 9: Heat capacities of PET-hemp composites compounded in a 250°C mixing chamber, data from the second experimental run

Fig. 11: Weight loss of various PET-hemp composites after 300°C of the first experimental run

Fig. 10: Heat capacities of PET-hemp composites compounded in a 260°C mixing chamber, data from the second experimental run